

C-Fe chains due to segregated Carbon Impurities on Fe(100)

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Abstract

Bulk carbon impurities segregate at the Fe(100) surface and, upon thermal annealing, can form metastable surface phases with local and long range order and peculiar electronic properties. We present a surface science study of C-segregated Fe(100) with scanning tunneling microscopy, angle resolved photoemission, and ab-initio calculations of the surface structure and electron states. In particular the $c(3\sqrt{2} \times \sqrt{2})$ structure, observed for 0.67 atomic layers of C segregated at the iron surface, is found to be due to self-organized carbon stripes made of zig-zag chains. The strong hybridization between C and Fe was observed in ARPES spectra.

Keywords: Scanning Tunneling Microscopy; Angle Resolved Photoemission; Surface Segregation; Self Assembly

1. Introduction

The surface segregation is the preferential enrichment of solute atoms on the surface, where the atoms come from the bulk in a condensed phase to its surface [1]. This usually happens at high temperature, that is, the annealing temperature of the sample is high enough that solute atoms in the bulk diffuse easily and reach the surface where they accumulate modifying the surface composition and electronic structure. Recent scanning tunneling microscopy (STM) experiments revealed the nano-scale structures of segregated surfaces, for example S/Fe(110) [2] and S/Fe(111) [3]. We have recently reported the nano structure observed with atomic resolution STM for C/Fe(001) [4, 5], which corresponds to the long range $c(3\sqrt{2} \times \sqrt{2})$ pattern observed by low electron energy diffraction (LEED). Ab initio calculations

[6] could reproduce the local structure as observed with STM. In this paper we present angle resolved photoelectron spectroscopy (ARPES) results associated with the local structure of C self-organized chains at the Fe(100) surface.

2. Experimental and calculation methods

The sample was a bcc Fe(100)3%Si single crystal. STM images presented flat terraces, about 10 nm wide, with monoatomic steps, which correspond to a misalignment of $\sim 1^\circ$ with respect to the (100) plane. Auger electron spectroscopy (AES) revealed, after sample annealing, the presence of C and P impurities. Sputtering (800V, Ar⁺) and annealing cycles were

performed to firstly remove residual contamination and subsequently to activate the segregation process. The segregation phenomena were observed reproducibly at different temperature intervals: C accumulates at the surface for temperature higher than 250 °C while P accumulates above approximately 580 °C. Si which is added in Fe single crystal for stabilizing the bcc structure was also observed with AES after the low temperature annealing but was replaced by C atoms after the onset of C segregation. That is, for annealing at temperature between 250 °C and 580 °C the only segregated element observed was C. The surface reconstructions studied were highly reproducible in many preparations. The experiments were performed at the APE-INFM (advanced photoemission experiment) beamline at Elettra storage ring in Trieste, in a vacuum better than 1×10^{-10} mbar. Room temperature STM images were taken at the sample preparation facilities of the APE beamline. The tip was electrochemically etched (1N NaOH solution) from tungsten wire and cleaned with sputtering-annealing procedure in ultra-high vacuum. Images were taken in constant current mode. The ARPES measurements were made at LE (low energy) branch of APE beamline equipped with a Scienta SES2002 electron energy analyzer. The total energy resolution was 20 meV for $h\nu=50$ eV radiation and the angle resolution is 0.2° . The APRES data were measured at room temperature.

Ab initio calculations were performed within density functional theory, using spin polarized Perdew-Burke-Ernzerhof exchange correlation functional [7] and Vanderbilt ultra soft pseudopotentials [8]. The details of the calculation is presented elsewhere [5,6].

3. Results and Discussion

The long range structure derived from LEED [4] is a $c(3\sqrt{2} \times \sqrt{2})$ structure which was also previously observed in the case of C adsorbates on Mo [9] and W (001) [10] surfaces. In the present case the size of the C reconstruction domains was about 2 nm. The Auger peak height ratio between C KLL peak and Fe LMM peak of $c(3\sqrt{2} \times \sqrt{2})$ structure is 1.3 times larger than that obtained for $c(2 \times 2)$ structure after annealing 300 °C for 8 min. The nominal coverage for this reconstruction is 0.67 monolayers (ML). AES intensity ratios varied by $\pm 7\%$ around this value for optimal preparations.

The wide region STM images observed for the $c(3\sqrt{2} \times \sqrt{2})$ pattern displayed a maze-like structure along $\langle 11 \rangle$ directions: i) The period perpendicular to the line direction is 1.5 times as large as the distance between two Fe atoms along

$\langle 11 \rangle$ direction of bcc Fe ($\sqrt{2} \times a$: a is the lattice constant of bcc Fe); ii) The lines do not exceed about 2 nm in length and either break or rotate 90° . At the breaking points, unsaturated "dangling" bonds are observed as white clouds [4, 5].

The atomically resolved STM image for $c(3\sqrt{2} \times \sqrt{2})$ structure is shown in Fig. 1(a). The image size is 2.4×3.0 nm and the bias voltage and tip current are +200 mV and 0.2 nA, respectively. The fine structure of the stripes clearly displays a zig-zag structure about the average $\langle 11 \rangle$ direction. Further evidence of the zig-zag structure is given by the cross section analysis (Fig. 1(b)). The solid (dashed) curve in Fig. 1(b) shows the cross section along the solid (dashed) line in Fig. 1(a). Distinct π phase shift between two curves is observed. The distance between the nearest neighbor atoms is approximately 0.29 nm and it is equal to the lattice constant of bcc Fe, that is, the distance between two Fe atoms in (100) surface. Now the unit cell of the C induced surface structure is shown in Fig. 1(a) by the white box. The unit cell is 3 times as long as $c(2 \times 2)$ or $(\sqrt{2} \times \sqrt{2})$ unit cell and the face centered position is equivalent to the corner position, this is the $c(3\sqrt{2} \times \sqrt{2})$ structure.

Fig. 1. (a) Atomically resolved STM image for C/Fe(100) $c(3\sqrt{2} \times \sqrt{2})$ structure after annealing at 550 °C. The image size is 2.4×3.0 nm. The unit cell is indicated by the white box. (b) Cross section curves of the two parallel lines (solid and dashed) along the zig-zag chain between A and A' in Fig. 1(a).

Fig. 2. Theoretical equilibrium surface structure of C/Fe(100) $c(3\sqrt{2} \times \sqrt{2})$. (Top view.) Small circles denote C atoms and light (dark) big circles denote top (second) layer Fe atoms. C atoms sit slightly off fourfold hollow sites.

Fig. 3. Normal emission spectra for clean Fe(100) (gray) and $c(3\sqrt{2} \times \sqrt{2})$ C/Fe(100) (black) surfaces.

Ab initio calculation [5, 6] identified the zig-zag chain structure as the lowest-energy configuration for 2/3ML on Fe(100) with $c(3\sqrt{2} \times \sqrt{2})$ surface structure. Figure 2 shows the equilibrium atomic structure obtained from the ab initio calculations for the C/Fe(100) $c(3\sqrt{2} \times \sqrt{2})$ structure. The C atoms are located close to the hollow site of Fe surface suggesting the formation of strong Fe-C bonds where C is fivefold coordinated [5, 6].

The calculations show that the electron density probed by the STM experiment is mostly due to Fe derived states. The zig-zag chains deeply modify the Fe electron states with respect to the clean Fe(100) surface. The electronic structure calculations predict a strong hybridization between C and Fe [9].

We measured ARPES of the valence bands for $c(3\sqrt{2} \times \sqrt{2})$ C/Fe(100) with linearly polarized light of $h\nu=50$ eV and $\langle 11 \rangle$ direction lying in the photoemission plane. In these conditions, k_{\parallel} of the photoelectrons is either along the chain axis or perpendicular to it. Figure 3 shows the comparison of the clean Fe(100) (gray) and

$c(3\sqrt{2} \times \sqrt{2})$ C/Fe(100) (black) surface spectra as measured at normal emission, over the whole occupied valence band energy range. Details of the energy interval between -7.5 eV and -1.5 eV are displayed in Figs. 4 where data measured with the $\langle 10 \rangle$ direction in the photoemission plane, i.e. k_{\parallel} at 45° from the chain axes, are also shown. The first two panels display reference data for clean Fe(100). Each spectrum in the stack was measured at a different emission angle: starting from normal emission ($k_{\parallel} = 0$, bottom spectrum), crossing the M (X) point for $\langle 11 \rangle$ ($\langle 10 \rangle$) direction and ending at $k_{\parallel}=2 \text{ \AA}^{-1}$ at Fermi energy (E_F) (top spectrum). The data for the $c(3\sqrt{2} \times \sqrt{2})$ C/Fe(100) surface are displayed in Figs. 4(c) and 4(d). Two surface states at -0.2 eV and -2.5 eV from E_F are seen in the clean Fe(100) normal emission spectrum [12]. The normal emission spectrum for C/Fe(100) shows a change in the surface states: two new distinct C induced surface states appear at around -12eV and -3.5 eV, which are C 2s and 2p derived states according to the band calculation. At normal emission one observes an increased binding energy of the leading peak, and a new peak appearing at about -1.3 eV. There is an other important change at -2.5 eV: the highly dispersive Fe(100) surface state is replaced by a dispersionless peak in the C-modified surface. If we consider the -3.5 eV peak, we note that its energy dispersion is larger when the experimental geometry corresponds to the chains aligned in the scattering plane (or perpendicular to it) ($\langle 11 \rangle$ spectra) than when the chains are oriented at $\pm 45^\circ$ in a plane perpendicular to the scattering plane ($\langle 10 \rangle$ spectra). Accordingly k_{\parallel} is along (or perpendicular) to the chains in the first case and at an angle of 45° in the latter. If we assume that perpendicularly to the chains the states should be dispersionless, then we may tentatively attribute the -2.5 eV peak to those while the largest measured dispersion should be attributed to the electron states extended along the chain axis. These attributions would correspond to a quasi-one dimensional character of the electron states of the zig-zag chains. We stress that in a previous report on scanning tunneling spectroscopy we showed that empty surface states at about +0.2 eV above E_F are present on the chains and absent in between the chains [5].

We also note that the spectra for C/Fe(100) in Fig. 5(a) do not show the O derived peak around 6 eV, which is observed, dispersionless, in the “clean” surface, corresponding to a minor contamination <0.2 ML of oxygen and/or carbon-oxide [5]. The peak around 6 eV observed near normal emission for C/Fe(100) is not due to O but to Fe sp bands which disperse towards the Fermi level for increasing k_{\parallel} values. The actual lack of oxygen related features at the surface, even after several hours in

UHV, is an indicator of a strong reduction of the surface reactivity of the $c(3\sqrt{2} \times \sqrt{2})$ structure to O and CO with respect to the pristine Fe(100) surface, in the residual gas pressure of the UHV chamber. This can be taken as a further, albeit indirect, indication of large changes in the iron surface electronic structure.

4. Conclusion

We have presented ARPES data for the $c(3\sqrt{2} \times \sqrt{2})$ C/Fe(100) surface that give evidence of large perturbation of the iron derived states. New dispersionless as well as dispersive peaks appear in the C modified surface that are consequent of Fe-C hybridization. The dispersive peak at -3.5 eV is attributed to quasi-one dimensional chain states, also in agreement with the DFT calculation.

Fig. 5. ARPES spectra. (a) and (b) for clean Fe(100). (c) and (d) for C/Fe(100). The orientation of k_{\parallel} vector of (a) and (c) is $\langle 11 \rangle$ direction, which corresponds that the k_{\parallel} vector is either along the chain axis or perpendicular to it. The orientation of k_{\parallel} vector of (b) and (d) is $\langle 10 \rangle$ direction, which corresponds that the k_{\parallel} vector lies at 45° from the chain axes. The value of k_{\parallel} of the top spectra is 2 \AA^{-1} at E_F .

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